

THE CONTEXT MEANING OF DEIXIS

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Abstract : Deixis is one of the important studies in pragmatics. It is a word or phrase that can refer to a person, place, or time in the speakers' utterance. Usually, each deixis has a different function. That function relies on the context of deixis both implicitly and explicitly. Then, the objective of this research is to find the types of deixis and divulge the function which is applied in the speaker utterance. It is important to understand the speaker's intends in communication by the use of context deixis.

Keywords: Pragmatics, Context Meaning, Deixis, Implicit meaning.

Pragmatics tells about the utterance with a context in its text, Bardovi-Harlig et al. (2010, v) said that “pragmatics deals with meaning-in-context, which for analytical purposes can be viewed from different perspectives (the speaker’s, recipient’s, analyst’s, etc.)”. That means a context that the speaker, the recipient, and the analyst have a different point of view. A little different concept was conveyed by Chovanec (2014: 16), “the broad conception of pragmatics is more of a shared general outlook on language in use that seeks to understand the relationship between speakers, language form, discourse structure and the variety of contexts in which interactions are embedded (social, cultural, historical, personal).” There is an interaction with general perception or general comprehension, but it still needs to understand the context of the discussion.

In general communication, it is necessary for people to understand the context, as Bublitz & Norrick (2011: 4) stated that “pragmatic is fundamentally concerned with communicative action in any kind of context.” Then “in the pragmatic perspective, language use and language users in interactions are primary”, it can be noted that the pragmatic is in peoples’ general communication with the related context is interacted. Pragmatic considers human communication, deals, and understands a context between the speaker and the recipient. It means dealing with a different perspective or context but it still related or it can be said that pragmatic is concerned with communicative utterance in any kind of context that intended to the speaker means.

Deixis is an important study in pragmatics when the listener (especially the music lovers) does not understand the context in a song lyric. A song lyric can be understood when the listener knows what the references are, or when,

and where the utterances are spoken. This also deals with the listeners who do not understand what the speaker means so that the communication cannot run properly because of their misinterpretation, (Sari: 2015). Therefore, Wati (2014: 61) said that deixis is used to explain and describe the reference and its function of personal, pronoun, time, demonstrative, lexical feature, and other that connects each other to the utterance with the relation of space and time.

On one hand, deixis in the novel, story, or script is clearly stated the reference of deixis either it is about *who, what, where, when, why, or how*, but Wibowo & Naulfar (2018: 83) claimed that people do not interested in reading because they do not understand one simple word meaning of reference in the text reading, then they often make one mistake of their reading. It just because they do not understand deixis used, so it could affect the meaning or message in the story or even in a whole novel will be misinterpreted. Thus, some people decide to read again. In some cases show that deixis word is not usually stated in the context explicitly. It is rather than a smaller matter in writing or speech but has an important role in communication. On the other hand, when deixis is applied in a song lyric, the context is interpreted implicitly, so it is not too clear if the listener just hearing without rendering a deep understanding. In Jarrah (2016) said that explicit meaning has a decoded meaning while implicit meaning has a communicated meaning.

Deixis as claimed by Yule (2010: 130), "These are words such as here and there, this or that, now and then, yesterday, today or tomorrow, as well as pronouns such as you, me, she, him, it, them." He continued, "They are technically known as deictic (/daiktik/) expressions, from the Greek word deixis, which means "pointing" via language." Then Dylgjeri & Kazazi (2013: 88) added that "Deixis does not only have the function of a grammatical constituent, but it has to point out the different meanings of the words have even in cases they are used in the same way in different situations." Deixis has a different meaning depends on the situation that the speaker said. According to Wibowo & Naulfar (2018: 75), "Deixis refers to some other word or something else to understand the meaning of specific words and phrase in an utterance based on the context. The words or phrases that need the context to convey the meaning are deictic." Deixis is a word that has a current context. The context of deixis called deictic.

Those mean deixis is a pointing word that not only has a function in grammatical constituent but also have a meaning or a context depend on the situation and the deictic function. Every deixis has a different point of view which has to be understood by the reader about its meaning or its function. For

example, there are *he, they, today, tomorrow, there, this, that, those, rainy day*, and so on. Deixis has reference categories according to their needs in the sentence or the utterance. There are 5 types of deixis conveyed by Alan Cruse (Nasution, Setiadi, & Ilza: 2018).

The deixis is a word or phrase that has an implicit or explicit context that can refer to a person or people, place, and time in its utterance. A context deals with the meaning of utterance that the speaker said and it is understood by both of the speaker and the listener. The deixis in pragmatic can avoid some misunderstandings in the context or meaning.

The use of deixis is not only in pointing person, time, and place but also in grammatical function. In interpreting the context of the deixis, people can pay attention from another lyric to know the information where the utterance is when the utterance is, and who the speaker of the utterance is. It can be seen that the understanding of deixis is important in communication or even in written text. It will avoid people to ask more and to repeat the utterance from the interlocutors, or when they read some written text then decide to reread what they have read because of lack in understanding the deixis word's reference.

To find the meaning of the songs lyric, the learners need the deixis understanding because one of the difficult things in learning English is referring word to the pointing words. Thus, deixis in pragmatic will help the learners in pointing person, pointing place, and pointing time according to the speaker's mean. Some suggestions, especially for English language learners and the readers, are to develop this research. It can be developed by revealing the meaning of the song's lyric as a whole through the concept of deixis. The writers also recommend to the other researchers to do the same research with other cases, the other researchers can develop this research from another field, corpus, or text to elaborate and innovate the understanding of deixis concept. Finally, this article will help the readers especially the listeners of those movie soundtracks more understand about deixes that are used in it or any texts.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

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